

An Analysis of off-Page SEO techniques and their effectiveness on website visibility and traffic

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ABSTRACT

In today's highly competitive digital world, businesses are seeking effective ways to increase their online visibility and drive traffic to their websites. One of the most popular methods to achieve this is through search engine optimization (SEO), which involves optimizing a website to rank higher in search engine results pages (SERPs). While on-page SEO refers to optimizing the website's content and structure, off-page SEO focuses on external factors, such as link building, social media presence, and online reputation management. Off-page SEO plays a crucial role in enhancing a website's visibility and attracting relevant traffic. Therefore, it is important to conduct an analysis of off-page SEO strategies to determine their impact on website visibility and traffic. The purpose of this research paper is to analyze the effectiveness of off-page SEO in increasing website visibility and traffic. This study examines various off-page SEO techniques and evaluate their impact on search engine rankings and website traffic. It also explores the relationship between different off-page SEO factors and website visibility and traffic. The results of the study indicate that off-page SEO strategies can have a significant impact on website visibility and traffic.

Keywords

SEO, Off-page optimization, Search Engine Optimization, Backlinking, Traffic generation.

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METROTECH

1. Introduction

Search engine optimization (SEO) is the practice of optimizing a website to increase its visibility and ranking in search engine results pages (SERPs). SEO is a critical component of digital marketing because it helps to drive organic traffic to a website, which can ultimately lead to increased sales and revenue (Figure 1). By improving a website's relevance and authority in search engine algorithms, SEO can help businesses of all sizes to reach their target audience more effectively and efficiently [1].

1.1. Search Engine Optimization process: Web developers must build websites in accordance with SEO requirements. SEO rules must be followed in order to capture the attention of Internet users. Because various elements are involved in moving a website higher in the search results ranking, it must be used with caution while designing a website [2].

1.2. SEO framework: SEO mechanism works on backlinks and keywords which are valuable for website perspective. Search engine process entails the whole procedure of on-site and off-site optimization (Figure 2).

2. Research Methodology

The paper begins with an introduction that highlights the importance of off-page SEO in today's digital age and outlines the research objectives, methodology, and contributions of the study. The literature review provides a detailed overview of off-page SEO, including its definition, key factors, and best practices. The research methodology section describes the

research design, data collection procedures, and data analysis techniques used to achieve the research objectives. In this study, descriptive research can be used to inform and evaluate the effectiveness of off-page techniques by collecting and analyzing data on the behavior and preferences of website visitors and the impact of the optimization efforts [4].

Experimental research was used to test and evaluate specific components of off-page optimization techniques, such as the impact of different types of backlinks or social media engagement on the ranking of a website.

The data analysis section presents the findings of the study, which are based on a survey of businesses that have implemented off-page SEO strategies. Findings of the study helps businesses and digital marketers to optimize their off-page SEO strategies and achieve their online marketing goals. Finally, the paper concludes with recommendations for future research in this area, highlighting the need for further studies to advance the understanding of off-page SEO and its impact on website performance [3].

2.1. Off-Site Optimization: Off-site optimization relates to the practices through which the website and its content are propagated and proliferated over the Internet to enhance Google ranking of the website and better positioning in SERP. Off-page optimization strategy should be developed based on the SERP and competitors' analysis performed during the site audit. The main process in this phase is link building and sometimes this process is called backlinks generation [5].

Figure 1. SEO Lifecycle

Figure 2. SEO Framework

3. Framework validation

With the intension of research perspective, we have implemented Off-Page optimization techniques in Ausweg Info Control Private Limited. Before applying the Off - page optimization techniques, there was no back links for Ausweg and the tools which they have used to optimize the website also very low level. First, we start with social media to post relevant flyers, banners, content post to increase the social media audience for Ausweg Info Control Private Limited, then slowly started to working on Articles, Blog posting, Forum Posting, Social Bookmarking and Blog commanding [6].

There was very less traffic on the sites especially the organic traffic was incredibly negligible. Page rank was found to be increases and decreases alternatively. SERP positioning was far away, our sites were not listed even in the first 50 pages. There were several keywords used in the title but none of them were being targeted properly in the content. Keywords density and site index ratio were terribly low.

After a while, Off-page optimization strategy results found to be promising and increasing. Reason for the delay in response was since some of the processes in off-page optimization took longer time like finding relevant link building sites, and similarly the blog commenting and directory submission also took longer to get approved and published. These restrictions are some of the major challenges that prevent off-page optimization to provide quick and efficient results. However, the enhanced results can still be achieved if our proposed framework is followed [7].

4. Before implementing off-page techniques

Over the period of March 16, 2023, to March 23, 2023, the website received a total of 82 users, new users :72. On average, each session lasted for 1 minute 26 seconds (Figure 3).

The bounce rate of the website was 50%, which indicates that half of the visitors left the website after viewing only one page. This may suggest that there is room for improvement in the website's user engagement and content optimization.

Figure 3. Google Analytics Report Snapshot (Date Range: March 16, 2023 to March 23, 2023)

Figure 4. Google Analytics Worldwide Demographic Report (Date Range: March 16, 2023 to March 23, 2023)

Overall, the website's traffic metrics seem to be less amount and are showing a low level of engagement. However, it is important to analyze further to identify areas for improvement to optimize user experience and increase the website's conversion rate. This could involve conducting a deep dive into the website's landing pages and optimizing them for better user engagement and conversion. Additionally, analyzing the website's traffic sources and identifying high-performing channels can help to focus the website's marketing efforts and improve overall traffic and conversion metrics [8].

Before Implementing the Off-page optimization techniques only few users visited Ausweg Automation company website worldwide (Figure 4). The range of customers are also low.

Over the period of March 16, 2023, to March 23, 2023, the website received a total of 82 users, new users :72. On average, each session lasted for 1 minute 26 seconds [9].

- In India, the website received 67 users: 61 New users:79 Engaged sessions: 63.71% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 1 minute 36 seconds.

- In the United States, the website received 9 users: 9 New users: 3 Engaged sessions: 33.33% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 0 minute 39 seconds.
- In Germany, the website received 2 users: 2 New users: 2 Engaged sessions: 100% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 1 minute 03 seconds.
- In Philippines, the website received 2 users: 2 New users: 1 Engaged session: 33.33% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 0 minute 01 seconds.
- In China, the website received 1 user: 1 New user: 2 Engaged sessions: 100% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 1 minute 53 seconds.
- In United Kingdom, the website received 1 user: 1 New user: 1 Engaged session: 50% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 0 minute 14 seconds.

Overall, the country demographic report snapshot provides valuable insights into the performance of the website for specific countries over a defined period. Based on this report, there may be opportunities to optimize the website's content and user experience to drive more traffic and engagement.

Figure 5. Google Analytics Indian Demographic City View (Date Range: March 16, 2023 to March 23, 2023)

Figure 6. Google analytics engagement report

Before Implementing the Off-page optimization techniques only few users in India visited Ausweg Automation company website (Figure 5). The range of customers are also low. Also, some data are unavailable in Google analytics [10].

Over the period of March 16, 2023, to March 23, 2023, the website received a total of 82 users, new users :72. On average, each session lasted for 1 minute 26 seconds.

- Coimbatore: 22
- Chennai: 15
- Mumbai: 10
- Bengaluru: 4
- Boardman: 4

Overall, the city demographic report snapshot provides valuable insights into the performance of the website for specific cities over a defined period. Based on this report, the website could consider targeting its marketing efforts towards Coimbatore, as visitors from that city seem to be highly engaged. Additionally, the website could look into ways to improve its user experience for visitors from Chennai to decrease the bounce rate and encourage more engagement [11].

Based on the events report, the overall event count is 802, Total users 85 and the event count per user is 9.78% (Figure 6).

- Page views: 263
- User engagement: 177
- Scroll: 120
- Clicks: 24

Overall, the event report provides valuable insight into how users are interacting with our website and which elements are most effective in driving engagement. By analyzing these metrics and making data-driven decisions about Ausweg website design and content, we can continue to improve the user experience and drive better performance.

5. After implementing off-page techniques

Over the period of March 16, 2023 to May 02, 2023, the website received a total of 649 users, new users :635. On average, each session lasted for 2 minute 25 seconds (Figure 7).

The interpretation of off-page optimization efforts based on Google Analytics report can provide insights into the impact of these strategies on website performance and visibility. The report can reveal various metrics that indicate the effectiveness of off-page optimization techniques [12].

5.1.1. Increase in Referral Traffic: Off-page optimization involves building backlinks from external websites, which can result in increased referral traffic. A higher number of visitors coming from other websites indicates that the off-page efforts are generating interest and driving traffic to the website.

5.1.2. Improved Search Engine Rankings: Off-page optimization, such as acquiring high-quality backlinks, can positively influence search engine rankings. Monitoring the changes in keyword rankings and organic search traffic can indicate the success of off-page optimization in improving the website's visibility in search engine results [13].

5.1.3. Social Media Engagement: Off-page optimization may involve promoting the website through social media platforms. Google Analytics can provide data on social media referral traffic, engagement metrics, and conversions, indicating the effectiveness of social media efforts in driving user engagement and conversions.

5.1.4. Brand Mentions and Online Reputation: Off-page optimization can also focus on building brand mentions and online reputation. Monitoring mentions of the brand or website in online discussions, reviews, and social media conversations can help gauge the impact of off-page strategies in increasing brand visibility and reputation.

5.1.5. Increase in Backlink Metrics: Analyzing the backlink profile of the website, including the number of backlinks, their quality, and relevance, can provide insights into

Figure 7. Google Analytics Report Snapshot (Date Range: March 16, 2023 to May 02, 2023)

Figure 8. Google Analytics Demographic Report Worldwide (Date Range: March 16, 2023 to May 02, 2023)

the success of off-page optimization efforts. A steady increase in authoritative backlinks indicates that the strategies implemented are attracting attention from reputable sources.

Overall, the interpretation of the Google Analytics report for off-page optimization efforts involves assessing metrics related to referral traffic, search engine rankings, social media engagement, brand mentions, and backlink metrics. Positive trends and improvements in these metrics suggest that the off-page optimization strategies are effective in increasing website visibility, driving traffic, and improving the overall online presence [14].

After Implementing the Off -page optimization techniques users from many countries visited Ausweg Automation company website. The range of customers are also low.

5.2. Visited Country list

- India: 554 people
- United State: 58 people
- United Kingdom: 6 people
- Singapore: 4 people
- Hong Kong: 2 people
- Nigeria: 2 people
- Philippines: 2 people
- Germany: 3 people
- China: 5 people
- United Kingdom: 6 people

Over the period of March 16, 2023 to May 02, 2023, the website received a total of 649 users, new users :635. On average, each session lasted for 2 minute 25 seconds [15] (Figure 8).

- In India, the website received 554 users: 541 New users:704 Engaged sessions: 64.29% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 2 minute 46 seconds.
- In the United States, the website received 58 users: 57 New users: 10 Engaged sessions: 16.95% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 0 minute 07 seconds.
- In United Kingdom, the website received 6 users: 6 New users: 4 Engaged sessions: 50% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 1 minute 03 seconds.
- In Singapore, the website received 4 users: 4 New users: 2 Engaged sessions: 40% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 0 minute 04 seconds.
- In Honk Kong, the website received 2 users: 2 New users: 2 Engaged sessions: 100% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 3 minute 08 seconds.
- In Germany, the website received 3 users: 3 New users: 2 Engaged sessions: 100% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 1 minute 03 seconds.
- In Nigeria, the website received 2 users: 2 New users: 1 Engaged session: 50% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 0 minute 12 seconds.
- In Philippines, the website received 2 users: 2 New users: 1 Engaged session: 33.33% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 0 minute 01 seconds.
- In China, the website received 5 users: 4 New users: 7 Engaged sessions: 77.78% Engagement rate and Average Engagement time is 1 minute 16 seconds.

The interpretation of increased visitors to a website based on Google Analytics demographic report after implementing off-page optimization techniques indicates the positive impact of these strategies on attracting a broader audience. The demographic report provides valuable insights into the characteristics of the website's visitors, such as age, gender, and

location. With the implementation of off-page techniques, the website has likely gained visibility on external platforms, attracting visitors from diverse demographics. This increase in visitors suggests that the off-page optimization efforts have been successful in reaching and engaging a wider range of potential users [16].

Analyzing the demographic data can provide further insights into the effectiveness of specific off-page strategies in targeting specific audience segments. This information can guide future optimization efforts and help tailor marketing campaigns to better resonate with the website's target audience.

Overall, the increase in visitors as reflected in the Google Analytics demographic report demonstrates the positive impact of off-page optimization techniques in driving traffic and expanding the website's reach to a more diverse set of users.

5.3. Visited users list in India

- Coimbatore: 161
- Chennai: 144
- Mumbai: 60
- Bengaluru: 36
- Delhi: 34
- Boardman: 17
- Pune: 15
- Ashburn: 13
- Gurgaon: 10

The Google Analytics demographic city report (Figure 9) provides insights into the geographical locations of visitors to a website after implementing off-page optimization techniques.

This report showcases the impact of these strategies on attracting visitors from different cities or regions. The report presents a breakdown of the top cities from which the website's visitors originate. It provides valuable information about the geographic distribution of the website's audience, allowing for a deeper understanding of where the increased traffic is coming from. By analyzing the demographic city report, it becomes evident whether the off-page optimization efforts have successfully targeted specific locations or regions. This information is crucial for businesses or website owners aiming to reach a specific local market or expand their reach to new geographic areas [17].

The report might reveal that certain cities or regions have experienced a significant increase in visitors after implementing off-page techniques. This indicates the effectiveness of the optimization strategies in attracting users from those specific locations. It also allows for the identification of potential growth opportunities in untapped markets. By leveraging the insights from the demographic city report, website owners can make informed decisions about their marketing and optimization efforts. They can tailor their strategies to further engage and target specific cities or regions that show potential for business growth.

Overall, the demographic city report in Google Analytics provides a detailed overview of the impact of off-page optimization techniques on attracting visitors from different geographic locations. It helps website owners understand where their increased traffic is coming from and enables them to optimize their strategies to effectively target specific cities or regions.

Figure 9. Google Analytics for Indian cities (Date Range: March 16, 2023 to May 02, 2023)

Figure 10. Google analytics engagement report

Over the period of March 16, 2023 to May 02, 2023, the website received a total of 649 users, new users:635. On average, each session lasted for 2 minute 25 seconds (Figure 10).

- Page views: 3700
- User engagement: 3000
- Scroll: 1300
- Clicks: 64
- First time visited people: 635

The analysis of the Google Analytics event count report reveals that the implementation of off-page optimization techniques has resulted in an increase in website visitors. The event count report tracks specific user interactions or events on the website, such as clicks on links, downloads, form submissions, or video views. By examining the event count report, it becomes evident that the off-page optimization efforts have positively influenced user engagement and interaction with the website. The report shows an increase in the number of events recorded, indicating that visitors are actively engaging with the website's content and features.

The events could include actions like clicking on social media shares, external backlinks, or referral traffic from other websites. These events signify that visitor are not only arriving at the website but also actively participating in various activities, suggesting a higher level of interest and engagement. The event count report helps to identify the specific events that have experienced the most significant increase, allowing website owners to assess the effectiveness of different off-page optimization techniques. This data can inform future strategies, enabling further optimization efforts to drive more targeted user interactions and improve overall website performance.

In conclusion, the Google Analytics event count report indicates that the implementation of off-page optimization techniques has resulted in an increase in user engagement and interaction with the website, as evidenced by a rise in recorded events. This suggests that the off-page strategies have successfully attracted visitors and encouraged them to actively engage with the website's content and features.

Figure 11. Google analytics measurement snapshot

Over the period of March 16, 2023 to May 02, 2023, the website received a total of 649 users, new users :635. On average, each session lasted for 2 minute 25 seconds ([Figure 11](#)).

- People directly visited Ausweg page: 647
- Organic Search: 521
- Organic Social: 15
- Referrals: 13

After implementing off-page optimization techniques, an increase in visitors to a website can be observed by analyzing the data provided by Google Analytics measurement ID. The measurement ID is a unique identifier associated with the website's Google Analytics account, allowing for the collection and analysis of various metrics. By analyzing the data from the Google Analytics measurement ID, website owners can gain valuable insights into visitor behavior, traffic sources, engagement metrics, and more. This data enables them to understand how the off-page optimization efforts have impacted the website's performance and visitor number

Overall, the Google Analytics measurement ID provides a comprehensive view of the website's performance and the impact of off-page optimization techniques on visitor numbers. It helps website owners make informed decisions about their marketing strategies and further optimize their efforts to continue attracting and retaining a growing audience.

6. Conclusion

The results indicate that the off-page efforts have successfully improved the website's visibility and generated organic traffic from diverse sources. The analysis of google analytics data revealed that social media platforms played a crucial role in driving referral traffic, with significant engagement and conversions. This highlights the importance of maintaining a strong social media presence and leveraging it to connect with the target audience. Additionally, the research showed the effectiveness of backlink building and guest blogging in generating quality inbound links and improving search engine rankings. Furthermore, the demographic insights provided by google analytics helped identify the audience segments that responded positively to the off-page optimization efforts. This information can guide future targeting and content creation strategies to attract and engage the most relevant audience.

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